

Demo: Latency-constrained deployment of cloud-native services in cloud federations

Fatemeh Tabatabaei†, Manuel Requena-Esteso†, Hamzeh Khalili†, Sarang Kahvazadeh†, Almudena Díaz-Zayas*, Jorge Márquez-Ortega*, and Josep Mangués-Bafalluy†

† *Services as networkS (SaS), Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Castelldefels, Spain*

* *Andalucía Tech, ITIS Software, Universidad de Málaga, Spain*

ftabatabaeimehr@cttc.es

Abstract—This paper demonstrates the federation of multiple clusters using Karmada within the context of multi-cluster 5G networks. Leveraging the robust architecture and flexible scheduling capabilities of Karmada, we present a new latency-aware scheduler plug-in for orchestrating cloud-native applications across diverse infrastructures. Our approach allows deploying latency-constrained cloud-native services in a resource-efficient manner. The demonstration encompasses geographically distributed clusters, illustrating the service deployment considering both latency and computational resources. The insights derived from this paper offer valuable solution for addressing stringent latency requirements in latency-constrained use cases (e.g., public protection and disaster relief), paving the way for advancements in multi-cluster management and application deployment strategies.

Keywords—Multi-cloud, federation, Karmada, scheduler, orchestration, latency-aware service placement

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of 5G has significantly broadened the possibilities in network communication, particularly in managing and deploying applications across diverse infrastructures. However, an ongoing challenge lies in efficiently deploying services that demand cutting-edge communication technology to meet stringent requirements for low latency, high-speed, and high bandwidth. These requirements are crucial for providing effective decision-making support during emergency and disaster scenarios, where multiple agencies deploy their resources in the emergency areas in a public protection and disaster relief (PPDR) context [1]. Ensuring data consistency and synchronization across multiple cloud-edge clusters becomes pivotal for real-time data analysis and decision-making. Addressing these latency issues and optimizing resource utilization are essential steps towards enhancing the effectiveness and responsiveness of latency-constrained services, ultimately improving emergency response and disaster management. This demonstration presents a framework enabling an efficient service deployment, thereby paving the way for innovative application strategies within the context of 5G networks.

II. DEMO ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1 illustrates the concept of cross-testbed federation [2], with a primary goal of establishing seamless connectivity

between the vertical and 5G-EPICENTRE [3] platform. The proposed solution focuses on enabling efficient communication between the vertical (e.g., PPDR) and the cross-testbed federation. Key to this solution is the utilization of Karmada [4] as the service orchestrator, facilitating the smooth deployment of cloud-native applications based on Propagation Policies (PPs) defined by user, across geographically distributed K8s clusters. The karmada scheduler has a pluggable framework that allows for the incorporation different strategies, shaping the scheduling behaviour. To meet the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specified by the services, we have developed custom scheduler plugin [5] objects. The scheduler utilizes a set of clientSets, to expose the API of clusters, retrieving aggregated available Central Processing Unit (CPU) resources. Additionally, it subscribes to a RabbitMQ broker topic to fetch cluster-to-emergency latency. We have integrated a Round-Trip Time (RTT) tracker module that periodically monitors response time to the Cloud cluster, encapsulating it as “rtt” payload and publishing it to RabbitMQ. To simulate latency within a cloud cluster, we employ the NETEM tool to replicate various real network conditions, including latency and jitter, enabling us to assess and evaluate the performance of our systems under realistic network scenarios. Prometheus agents are deployed using a Helm chart in the monitoring namespace of all clusters. When a service is deployed, Prometheus server and Prometheus alert manager communicate to the Kubernetes API to obtain the requested CPU of the deployed service. These metrics are then made available to Grafana for visualization purposes.

III. DEMONSTRATION WORKFLOW

To demonstrate the benefits of our approach, we showcase latency-constrained deployments of cloud-native services in a multi-cluster federation environment. The objective is to deploy the service in the cloud cluster, leveraging its abundant resources, provided that the latency requirements are met. If the latency requirements cannot be fulfilled, the service will be load-balanced across the edge clusters. This approach ensures efficient resource utilization while prioritizing the latency criteria for an efficient and reliable deployment. In our demonstration, we consider geographically distributed testbeds consisting of two clusters in the EXTREME Testbed® of the CTTC and one cluster in the Victoria Network of the University of Málaga (UMA) all joined to Karmada. The k8s cluster named uma-cluster in the UMA testbed Figure 1b, with 40

Figure 1 a) Demo architecture b) Demo flow showcasing member clusters and deployments c) The measured RTT by RTT tracker module before and after adding NETEM.

CPU cores, is considered the cloud DC. The two clusters named member-ti-nem and member-ti-nem3 in CTTC, with 16 and 12 CPU cores, respectively, are designated as edge1 and edge2 clusters. All deployments in our demonstration are based on nginx service deployment version 1.24.0, which is configured to request CPU cores and latency to mimic the characteristics of PPDR services. To address the unbalanced available CPU resources in the edge clusters, we have deployed two background services in edge1 cluster, consuming a total of 6 CPU cores. This deployment ensures that the available CPU in the edge1 cluster remains consistent at 10 CPU. In the initial step, we run RTT tracker to periodically measure the ping time to UMA cluster which under normal condition is around 26 ms. We then deploy a nginx service, nginx-40, requesting 1 CPU and a latency of 40 ms as a latency-sensitive service. Since the requested latency is higher than the measured RTT, the latency requirement of the first service is fulfilled, and it is deployed in the UMA cluster (cloud). As a second step, to emulate latency, NETEM is configured with 20 ms delay and 10 ms jitter, resulting in an increased RTT of approximately 50 ms (Figure 1 c). The second deployment, nginx2-40, is identical to the first one. However, considering the increased latency in the cloud cluster, the scheduler deploys the service in edge2 cluster, which has more available CPU resources. The final deployment, nginx-5, involves a service requesting a latency of 5 ms, indicating an extremely strict delay requirement. For this reason, the service is deployed in edge2 cluster, which has more available resources. The monitoring dashboard reports all the deployments in terms of CPU request for edge clusters.

IV. DEMO OVERVIEW

The goals of this demo are twofold. Firstly, we aim to show the capability of the Karmada orchestrator, which enables the federation of multiple K8s clusters across geographically distributed testbed infrastructure within the project. Secondly, we present our novel integration of a clusterResource plugin of Karmada’s scheduler. This plugin address service placement by taking into account key metrics such as latency and computational resources, which makes it suitable to solve the stringent requirements of PPDR use cases, while also providing valuable insights applicable to other domains.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was partially funded by EU Horizon 2020 grant 101016521 (5G-EPICENTRE), MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 grant PID2021-126431OB-I00 (ANEMONE), and Generalitat de Catalunya 2021 SGR 00770.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sterle, J., Mesogiti, I., Korsic, L., Theodoropoulou, E., Setaki, F., Lyberopoulos, G., ... & Klonidis, D. (2022, June). A Framework to Support the Deployment of PPDR Services Across Edge and Cloud Domains. In *IFIP International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations* (pp. 44-52).
- [2] D4.4 5G-EPICENTRE Experimentation facility preliminary version”, June 2022.
- [3] <https://www.5gepicentre.eu>

- [4] Karmada: Open, Multi-Cloud, Multi-Cluster Kubernetes Orchestration. available at: <https://karmada.io>
- [5] F. Tabatabaei, H. Khalili, M. Requena, S. Kahvazadeh and J. Manges-Bafalluy, "Dynamic Service Placement in 6G Multi-Cloud Scenarios," *2023 23rd International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, Bucharest, Romania, 2023, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICTON59386.2023.10207547.5G-EPICENTRE, "